

The Effects of Globalization on African Traditional Religious Culture: The Need for Redress

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Abstract

Globalization is a historical process resulting from human innovation and technological progress. It aims at cultural homogenization, posing the risk that Nigeria's culture may eventually transform into American or Western culture, with negative implications for the Nigerian nation. Globalization has significantly affected Nigerian culture in numerous ways. This paper aims to examine the effects of globalization on African Traditional Religious culture. A qualitative research design was adopted, with data sourced from secondary materials such as books, journal articles, periodicals, and the internet. The findings reveal that Western religion is being promoted, while African Traditional Religion, with all its rich offerings, is being relegated to the background. This has led to the erosion of our rich cultural heritage. The writer concludes that globalization has inflicted substantial damage on our cultural heritage and has negatively impacted the lifestyle of Nigerians, underscoring the need for redress. The writer recommends that our education system should be tailored to meet the needs of individuals and communities in promoting the use of our languages, and focusing on character development.

Keywords: Globalization and African Religion

Introduction

The history of globalization can be traced back to the period between 1450-1500 AD, this period is known as the era of mercantilism, when many powerful nations sought to expand their markets. The free movement of people, goods, and services has since transformed the world into a global village. Initially viewed as an economic issue, globalization is still often defined in economic terms. However, it is now clear that, although driven by economic motives, globalization affects all aspects of life, including politics, culture, technology, and religion¹. Africans have often been skeptical about the benefits of globalization. Some African commentators argue that the continent has not benefited much from globalization and that it has worsened poverty in Africa. In fact, some blame globalization for many of Africa's problems².

Globalization's impact on African culture has raised concerns. Bryan notes that globalization is pushing the world toward a single market economy, a single liberal democracy, and ultimately, a single Westernized cultural heritage.³ Zaremba warns that African culture is being diluted to the point of atrophy. This concern is valid, as culture is not just about business; it is also about identity and unity. Losing one's culture means losing one's identity.⁴ Alubo echoes this, saying, "A society cut off from its roots may thrive for a while on its own momentum, but eventually it will wither like cut flowers in a vase." This highlights the threat globalization poses to African cultural and religious values⁵. Globalization is believed to aim for the emergence of a single global culture and religion, with American culture and religion likely dominating. This is seen as Americanization, indicating a deliberate effort by America to impose its culture and religion on the world.⁶

Globalization has been defined in various ways by different authors. Twiss and Bruce see it as the closer integration of countries and peoples, breaking down barriers to the flows of goods, services, capital, knowledge, and people across borders. They describe it as creating a global market of investment, trade, and information through integrating economic decision-making worldwide⁷. Kosmin and Keysar define globalization as the intensification of worldwide social relations, where distant localities are interconnected in a way that local events

are influenced by happenings many miles away and vice versa⁸. Ritzer views globalization as a multifaceted process involving cultural, economic, and political relationships on a global scale. Key actors in this process include transnational corporations, multilateral institutions like the World Bank, International Monetary Fund, World Health Organization, and the media⁹. This pervasive nature of globalization affects humanity significantly, impacting society, labor markets, inequality, consumption, health, political stability, and legitimacy. It is a universal reality requiring adaptation to a global village for every part of the world.¹⁰

African Religion and Globalization

Religion and globalization are like two Siamese twins that involve two basic possibilities; religious responses to globalization and religious interpretation of globalization. Many religious commentators understand globalization as economic, imperialistic and homogeneous process¹¹. They share the economic/political perspective evaluating globalization as anywhere from a threatening challenge to the manifestation of evil in the world. Religion and globalization persistently engage in a flexible relationship, in which the former relies on the latter in order to thrive and flourish while at the same time challenging globalization. In many respects, globalization in the segment of the literature is a successor term for what used to be censured as the capitalist system. This is why Zaremba said that "globalization is a threat to religion and religion is the greatest resistance to globalization". Accordingly, globalization results in religion's violence and the unjust oppression of the majority of people around the world.¹²

For instance, between 1980 and 1995, there were 72 civil wars based on (ethnic, national, religious and racial grounds), as well as another type of war (state against state). This continued after the 1995 (aggression in Yugoslavia in 1999, civil war in Angola, Liberia, Sudan and bloody ethnic conflicts in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo and military intervention in Afghanistan).¹³It threatens local and indigenous cultures and religions, imposing a particularly burden on women. For example, Moreira said that "The colonialists came with the belief that women were to remain creatures of the private domain. Women were to preoccupy themselves with domestic issues and leave the 'real work' of ruling and running the nation in terms of politics and economics in particular to the men. The role and position of the pre-colonial African women did not conform to this concept of women."¹⁴

Hence, the implementation of policies seated in this myopic perception of women led to the erosion of women's position in society". This was the socialization that African society had to adopt. Another segment of both the religiously inspired and the secular literature see a much closer relation between globalization and religion, it is said that religion has essential role in shaping globalization. Globalization is one of the forces that have in the past been instrumental in binding different regions of the world together. With globalization, religious institutions such as Christianity, Islam and Hindu have spread throughout the world. Globalization no doubt, has affected African Traditional Religion in several ways for instance, globalization promotes the spread of Western culture and values, which often overshadow and dilute traditional African practices and beliefs.¹⁵

As Western lifestyles, media, and consumer habits become more dominant, traditional religious practices may be viewed as outdated or less relevant. The influence of Western religions, particularly Christianity and Islam, has grown with globalization. These religions often compete with and sometimes replace traditional African religious practices. Missionary activities and the global spread of Western religious institutions contribute to this shift. Traditional African religions are deeply tied to the cultural and social identity of African communities. As globalization encourages homogenization, there is a risk of losing these unique cultural identities. The younger generation, influenced by global culture, might adopt new beliefs and practices, moving away from their traditional roots. Globalization brings economic changes that can affect traditional practices. Urbanization and the push for modernity can lead to the abandonment of rural areas where traditional practices are more prevalent. Economic pressures may also force people to prioritize economic survival over maintaining traditional religious practices etc.¹⁶

Agents of Globalization in Africa

The agents of globalization in Africa include various entities and processes that facilitate the spread of global influences and integration into the global system. These agents contribute to cultural, economic, political, and social changes across the continent. Global media companies, films, music, and television shows contribute to the spread of Western culture and values. The proliferation of satellite television, streaming services, and social media platforms has made it easier for people in Africa to consume global content. Entities like the United Nations, World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), and World Trade Organization (WTO) play a crucial role in shaping policies and providing financial aid and development assistance. Their programs often come with conditions that promote market liberalization and integration into the global economy.¹⁷

The movement of people across borders for education, work, or refuge spreads ideas, cultural practices, and knowledge. Africans in diaspora also contribute to globalization by sending remittances and maintaining cultural connections with their home countries. Global educational standards, curricula, and institutions influence African education systems. Partnerships with foreign universities, scholarships, and international students contribute to the exchange of knowledge and ideas. International NGOs often bring new practices, technologies, and ideas to African countries. They work on various issues, including health, education, and human rights, promoting global standards and practices. The influx of international tourists exposes African communities to global cultures and practices. It can also lead to the commodification of local cultures and traditions to cater to tourist expectations.¹⁸

Aid from foreign governments and international bodies often comes with specific guidelines and expectations that promote certain economic and social models aligned with global standards. The diffusion of technology, including mobile phones, computers, and renewable energy solutions, connects Africa to global technological advancements and fosters innovation. Globalization encourages African nations to adopt political and economic reforms that align with international norms, such as democratization, market liberalization, and privatization. Multinational Corporations (MNCs) are large companies that operate in multiple countries, bringing investment, technology, and management practices to African economies. While they can create jobs and stimulate economic growth, they can also out compete local businesses and influence local cultures.¹⁹

Trade agreements and economic partnerships enhance the exchange of goods, services, and ideas, increasing Africa's exposure to global markets and consumer culture. Advances in telecommunications and widespread internet availability have connected Africa to the global information network, facilitating communication, information exchange, and access to global media, which influence local cultures and lifestyles. These agents collectively drive globalization in Africa, bringing both opportunities and challenges. News media like BBC, CNN, VOA, Radio France International, film shows, internet facilities, and television accelerate the integration of global culture. As a result, teenagers worldwide watch the same videos, listen to the same music, and wear the same clothes. Television audiences in nearly all countries watch the same major events, financial forecasts, and glimpses of ecological disasters, with these programs primarily disseminating American and European information. Consequently, individuals' economic welfare is increasingly impacted by global views, while local cultures and values are supplanted by foreign influences.²⁰

Effects of Globalization on African Religion and Culture

The Western concept of globalization as "invisible forces operating beyond human control that are transforming the world" is misleading. Propagated in this form, globalization may serve to justify the spread of Western culture and capitalist society.²¹ Maduagwu asserts that globalization results from the expansion of European culture through colonization and cultural imitation. It is closely tied to capitalist development, influencing political and cultural arenas. He further argues that globalization's goal is not merely to Westernize and capitalist the world but to make Western culture the standard by which all other cultures are measured. As he puts it: "every set of social arrangements must establish its position in relation to the capitalist West."²²

For the critics of globalization, it is mere deception to suggest that globalization is a self-propelling social dynamics. However, Maduagwu described it as economic sphere being directed by the World Trade Organization (WTO), with its underlying goal of economic liberalization; in political and cultural spheres, through the powerful means of information technology, dominated by the West. The weak cultures may not be able to resist the forces of globalization but the third world countries should not be unaware of the "hidden agenda" of globalization²³. The apparent truth about globalization is that it is the latest under current principle of economic exploitation of the Third World by the technological advanced countries, particularly of the West. It is no wonder that third world scholars have concentrated their reaction to globalization to its economic dimension. For the Third World, the conclusion of the Uruguay Round negotiations and the establishment of the WTO have risen to a new world order extending far beyond traditional international trade relations.²⁴

The situation in Africa today is so pathetic as a result of the gradual admittance of Western culture at the detriment of our own culture. Africa has consequently changed from a land of culture, nature; of tradition and rural setting where the cockcrow signals the dawn of a new day, to a land of urban dwellers with all the evils associated with it. Not only this, the formal ways of life of the African origin has been altered in much diversity, take for example African traditional religion, with all it has to offer, is driven to the background. It is the Western religion that is now promoted. The worship and belief of our gods and goddesses has been washed away by the belief and worship of one God. The basis of our religion is the root of our behavior and hence our belief and trust has been replaced by what we have been told is better than what we have; we have thrown away the trust and confidence in ourselves.²⁵

The problems caused by mass media and internet in recent times have caused serious effects to Africans. On the social front, the problems are endemic. Crime is promoted daily as a result of globalization popular among this is the cyber- crime all over the world, armed robbery is also accorded a professional status for young men and women. Fear rules the night of African man and despair rules the day. The man in public office turns corruption to his god. Pages of newspapers and magazines are filled with scandalous reports of one corrupt practice or other. Nigerian newspapers for example, reports daily occurrences of public office holders' involvement in bribery and corruption. Even those people that supposed to protect the law are indicted of one corruption or the other.²⁶

Societal restrictions on sex have diminished. Married men and women compete with singles in sexual pursuits, and even the younger generation uses the internet to find spouses, bypassing traditional courtship. Adultery is seen as a conquest and fornication as enjoyment. Hotels and brothels profit from this trend. Media such as BBC, CNN, VOA, Radio France International, films, the internet, and television accelerate the integration of global culture. Consequently, teenagers worldwide watch the same videos, listen to the same music, and wear similar clothes. Television audiences globally view the same events, financial forecasts, and ecological disasters, primarily disseminating American and European content. This global influence impacts economic welfare and supplants local cultures and values.²⁷

Additionally, education has shifted from traditional methods to more secular and cellular forms. Indigenous and civic/moral education that promoted obedience, brotherhood, love, and respect for elders and authorities has been overshadowed by Western education. This foreign culture embedded in Western education has severely impacted African culture, almost erasing it. Many Africans now prefer imported goods over locally made ones, regardless of quality, seeking validation from foreign labels like "Made in England," Japan, China, etc.²⁸.

Western education has created a generation of Africans with a colonial mentality. Many educated Africans discourage their children from speaking their native language, favoring English instead. Even when someone from their village speaks the native language, the children respond in English, claiming they understand but cannot speak it. Consequently, Western education has Westernized Africans to the point where they often no longer value their own culture. Many now view their cultural practices as uncivilized, primitive, and outdated. Globalization has not only impacted religion and education but also individual lives, families, and societies. Traditional practices

have been replaced: people no longer eat with their hands from a calabash but use silver spoons, golden plates, and stainless steel forks and knives. Instead of sitting on the floor with a traditional mat, they now relax on armchairs around modern dining tables. These changes reflect the influence of globalization and Western education on African lifestyles.²⁹

Globalization profoundly affects youth, causing them to lose touch with their cultural values. This loss is evident in their adoption of foreign cultures, dressing styles, dancing, and language, which impacts social life. Colonization and globalization, driven by modern technology, have introduced many changes. Colonization brought bureaucratic arrangements, new political systems, religions, Western education, and judicial systems. Modern technology led to urbanization, changes in family roles and patterns, a monetized economy, materialism, mass media growth, mobility, and the creation of a global community. While these factors are not inherently harmful, they have contributed to negative impacts on African society. Bureaucratic arrangements intended to simplify administration instead fostered bribery and nepotism due to competition for scarce resources like employment, scholarships, and economic advantages.³⁰

Globalization has led to various issues such as immodesty, nudity, individualism, consumerism, and the rise of lazy and corrupt elite in Africa. These problems stem from Africa's reliance on foreign legal codes that undermine self-determination in adjudication and dispute resolution, sidelining the communitarian nature of African societies. Globalization has also imposed a Western-style democracy that is confusing to many and too costly for developing economies, further entrenching Africa's dependency. This dependency has paved the way for cultural imperialism, disguised as globalization. To maintain this dependency on the West, militaristic intimidation and economic sanctions are often used, as seen in the attempts to suppress Robert Mugabe of Zimbabwe some years ago.³¹

Missionaries who came to Africa preached, converted souls, and built churches and mosques, causing serious problems for African religious practices. They condemned most African religious practices, using derogatory terms such as fetish, devilish, and Satanic to describe them. Converted Africans joined the missionaries in maintaining this negative view of their own religion. They condemned African forms of sacrifice and worship, traditional healing methods, and worldviews, introducing bio-medicine and ascribing negative terminologies to African practices. As a result, the rich African religion and practices were eroded. The foreign religion, with its beliefs, changed the African lifestyle and belief system.³²

Benefits of Globalization

Globalization has significantly improved learning methods in Nigerian society, which were once focused primarily on trade, agriculture, and creative arts. Today, people have ventured into diverse fields of knowledge and are excelling. Traditional African medicines have advanced and now rival orthodox medicine. Education has fostered global relations, enabling Nigerians to learn from other cultures and aspire to goals beyond agriculture, trade, and craftsmanship. Although traditional education remains active in many communities, it is often insufficient for meeting the challenges of the 21st century.³³

Through global interactions, Nigerians have advanced their technical knowledge, enhancing healthcare quality and other social services. Transportation has significantly improved, and communities strive to enjoy global standards of social services like electricity, potable water, and good roads. Technology has enabled the construction of important infrastructure such as power stations and dams, benefiting the nation greatly. Economically, globalization has created more opportunities for artisans and business people, improving quality of life and economic prosperity. It has boosted international trade, eased foreign investment, and facilitated capital flow to communities.³⁴ Globalization has helped Nigerians discard unethical cultural practices. Treating women as possessions and early marriages for girls are no longer common, and women now play greater roles in the community. While polygamy is declining, issues of divorce and concubines are rising. Religiously, globalization has encouraged Nigerians to abandon irrational superstitions like killing twins and human sacrifices, freeing people from groundless fears.³⁵

The Need for Redress

In the African continent and Nigeria in particular, the rate at which our culture is fast declining at the expense of western culture is quite pitiable. We have allowed the white man's culture to overshadow that of ours in our own land. This is not good and as such needs to be addressed urgently. There is need for us to preserve our cultural heritage like: respect for elders, our dress code and our native language. Respect for elders use to be common among Africans, seniority is associated with old age, experience; they make peace and are regarded as the custodians of our culture and traditions. They are also been regarded as being wise. No one insults or curses an elder likewise will one want an elder to curse him or her. However, in our contemporary societies today, most people insult and attack elders in fight. These habits are alien to African and the situation may continue if we do not change the trend. Since disrespect among the Africans is something strange, let us cultivate the habit of respecting our elders because if Nigerians continue with the habit of disrespecting their elders, they may find it difficult to change the future thereby passing the ugly trend to the coming generation³⁶

The issue of dress code is also worrisome too. The African man and woman were usually associated with modesty, dignity and honour by their mode of dressing. This however, seems to have changed, since Africans now dress to imitate the western culture; what our boys' and girls' wear is nothing to write home about. The girls go about almost half naked, all in the name of fashion, while some boys put on earrings, plait their hair and wear oversized jeans and shirts. They forgot that our African traditional clothes remain the best and as a matter of fact, are doing well even in the European markets. The African beauty in us will only come out if we dress like real Africans. We Africans should therefore, have a real orientation as to what our dressing codes should be.³⁷

Another issue of upmost concern is our native spoken language. If one looks around, one will discover that the native African languages are being suppressed by the western foreign languages such as English. In most African homes, people no longer use their native language to communicate. They prefer to use English language. Language should be something we must value; this is because in languages, we find our identity. During the colonial era, the whites did everything possible to suppress our local languages; they even went as far as trying to suppress our local names. Now the white man is not here with us but we ourselves are the ones suppressing our local native languages. It is dangerous to substitute our native language for a foreign one. It is good that we have a good knowledge of our local tribe, Africans should therefore, cultivate the habit of learning to read and write in their native language if not we stand the chance of losing our languages in the next fifty years or so.³⁸

Finally, every African should see it as his or her responsibility to ensure that, our cultural heritage is preserved. Africa is rich and beautiful well blessed with human and natural resources; that's why the white man looted most of our cultural values and took them to the European museums. The little we have left here should not be allowed to be destroyed again, let the African man and woman stand up and join in the fight for preserving our cultural heritage.³⁹

Conclusion

Globalization has brought significant changes to Nigerian culture, leading to both positive and negative effects. On the one hand, it has facilitated economic growth, technological advancement, and access to global knowledge. On the other hand, it has also led to the erosion of traditional values, practices, and identities. Western cultural dominance, particularly through media, education, and religion, has overshadowed and marginalized Nigerian cultural heritage, resulting in a loss of cultural diversity and identity. The negative implications of this cultural homogenization are profound. They threaten the rich tapestry of Nigeria's cultural heritage, diminishing the unique practices and beliefs that have been passed down through generations. This cultural erosion can weaken social cohesion, disrupt community life, and lead to a sense of disconnection among individuals from their cultural roots.

Given these challenges, there is a pressing need for redress. It is essential to actively preserve and promote Nigerian culture and traditional values. This can be achieved by integrating cultural education into the curriculum,

encouraging the use of indigenous languages, and fostering an environment where traditional practices are respected and celebrated. Moreover, there should be efforts to support and revitalize African Traditional Religions and cultural practices, ensuring they remain a vibrant part of Nigerian society. On a whole, while globalization brings many benefits, it is crucial to address its adverse effects on Nigerian culture. By taking deliberate steps to preserve and promote Nigeria's cultural heritage, we can maintain our cultural identity and ensure that future generations remain connected to their rich cultural roots. This balance between embracing global progress and safeguarding cultural heritage is vital for the holistic development of Nigerian society.

Recommendations:

1. African traditional religious teachings and cultural practices should be integrated into school curricula to ensure younger generations appreciate and understand their heritage.
2. Nigeria should invest in the research, documentation, and preservation of traditional knowledge, including medicinal practices, rituals, and folklore, through the establishment of archives and museums.
3. There is need to leverage technology by utilizing digital platforms to promote African traditional religions, disseminate information, and engage with a wider audience.
4. African languages, foods, and traditional attire should be actively promoted and encouraged.

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